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**EFFECT OF FLIPPED CLASSROOM INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY ON ELECTRICAL
INSTALLATION AND MAINTENANCE WORK STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT IN GOVERNMENT
TECHNICAL COLLEGES OF GOMBE STATE**

Barde, M. Y.¹ and Ezugu, L. C.²

¹ Department of Electrical/Electronic Technology Education, School of Secondary Education (Technical), Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi, Kano State

² Department of Electrical Technology Education, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Adamawa State

Corresponding Author: muhammedyaubarde@gmail.com, 09030043757

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of flipped class-room instructional strategy on Electrical installation and maintenance works (EIMWT) students' Achievement in GTCs in Gombe State, Nigeria. Electrical installation and maintenance works is a trade designed to provide both knowledge and skill that enable learners to efficiently perform in all aspect of Electrical installation and maintenance works and become self-reliant. Two (2) research questions and one (1) null hypothesis were set to guide the study. The study employed quasi-experimental research design. The experiment was carried out on all NTCII EIMWT students at Government Technical College Barunde, Kwami and Government Technical College Tula, in Gombe state. The study consisted of experimental group and control group each treated independently. The experiment lasted for a period of four (4) weeks. The test instrument used was 40 multiple choice questions adopted from NABTEB past question papers. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions, while ANCOVA was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The key findings of the study revealed that the flipped classroom teaching strategy improved the academic Achievement of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students and lecture teaching method. The study among others recommends that Policymakers and curriculum planners should incorporate flipped classroom instructional strategy into official technical education curricula and teacher training programs to ensure sustainable adoption and to improve students' Achievement outcomes in Government Technical Colleges.

Keywords: Flipped Classroom, Students' Achievement, Technical Colleges

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, technical colleges have been making efforts to improve the methods of teaching that will assist students improve their knowledge and mastering in their respective trades. The reasons for poor Achievement in classes lies in the traditional methods of transmitting knowledge to students (Malik et al., 2021). Technological integration in education ideally includes using technological tools and devices (like computers, projectors, software, or online platforms) to enhance teaching and learning. This approach is often overlooked or underutilized in actual practice. The system generally uses conventional learning environments where instructors present contents in class, and learners take notes and then go home to study on their own in preparation for examinations. They take examinations to demonstrate their understanding of the subject

matter (Braison & Durkin, 2021). This limits the amount of time students have to practice and allow the teacher to determine if the student can perform at a single moment (Tayebinik & Puteh, 2018). To overcome the challenges of the traditional teaching methods there is the need for the use of modern teaching strategy such as flipped classroom.

The flipped classroom is a teaching approach where traditional concepts on content delivery and engagement are inverted (the traditional activities normally done in the classroom are given to students as homework and traditional homework activities become classroom activities). The flipped classroom is an approach that replaces in-class lectures with collaborative practical activities and the requirement that students go through the course materials at their own time (Chen, Wang, Kinshuk, & Chen, 2014). Learners utilize digital tools to access recorded video lectures online, and the instructor assigns practical work, research activities, discussions, or any other assignment that may help the learners to better understand the content. This process is beneficial since students have time to digest the topic by watching the video being presented at their own pace and convenience and to ask questions during classes (Yaraner & Kaymakci, 2019). This could increase student engagement, interactivity, and motivation for learning. DeLozier and Rhodes (2017) defined the flipped classroom as the teaching practice of teachers which occurs by assigning lectures outside of class and devoting class time to a variety of learning activities.

Lecture method is one of the oldest methods of teaching. It is the process whereby the teacher does all the talking on a subject to the students. According to Mezieobi (2013), it is an age long traditional method of teaching in which knowledge or information are presented, conveyed, imparted or transferred to learners by the teacher who dominates the authoritarian teaching-learning process. Ekwue (2014) view lecture method as a straight forward transmission of information to students by means of printed materials or lecturers reading from printed materials and talking are simultaneously used with some groups of students. This method is one of the means through which the teacher communicates with his student and it is teacher centered method. Singh (2017) refers to lecture method as a process where the teacher delivers a lecture on a particular topic actively and the students listen to him as passive listeners. The method is characterized with listening on the part of the students and that is not too ideal to teach secondary school students. That's why Singh (2017) called it telling method and this may greatly affect the academic Achievement of students.

Academic Achievement is the outcome of education, denoting the degree to which a learner, educator, or institution has achieved their educational objectives. Typically, it is evaluated through tests or continuous assessment (Ikwuka & Samuel, 2017). Academic achievement or academic Achievement is the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has attained their short or long-term educational goals. Completion of educational benchmarks such as secondary school, diploma and bachelor's degree represent academic achievement. Academic achievement is commonly measured through examinations or continuous assessments but there is no general agreement on how it is best evaluated or which aspects are most important. Student academic Achievement has to do with the successful accomplishment of goals, measured by the extent to which instructional objectives are achieved. According to Eze and Osuyi (2018), academic achievement is a measure of the degree of success in performing specific tasks in a subject area or area of study by students after a learning experience. Whereas Ahmad and Ombuguhim, (2020) defined achievement as the scholastic standing of a student at a given moment in learning both theoretical and practical skills in Electrical/Electronic. Therefore, is essential to students' progress in the changing world of technology.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

There has been increasing concern over the quality of education and the achievement of students in technical subjects, particularly in the field of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade (EIMWT) in Government Technical Colleges of Gombe State, Nigeria. Despite efforts to improve teaching methods, many students continue to struggle with mastering practical and theoretical aspects of electrical installation, which is crucial for their skill development and future employment.

Traditional instructional strategies, have been found to be less effective in engaging students and enhancing their problem-solving and critical thinking skills. This has led to suboptimal Achievement in both theoretical and practical examinations, as well as limited hands-on competence in real-world scenarios. With the growing emphasis on the need for innovative teaching approaches, there is a need to explore alternative instructional methods that can better cater for the needs of students in vocational education such as flipped classroom instructional strategy.

However, there is limited research on the impact of this strategy on students' achievement in technical courses, particularly in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade in Gombe technical colleges. The problem of this study is that the extent to which this strategy can improve students' academic Achievement and practical skills acquisition in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade (IEMWT) compared to traditional teaching methods is not certain. If this is not ascertained, it will be difficult to improve the teaching and learning of EIMWT in Gombe State Technical Colleges.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study was to determine the effects of flipped class-room instructional strategy on Electrical installation and maintenance works (EIMWT) students' achievement in GTCs in Gombe State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the effect of flipped classroom Instructional Strategy on Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students' Achievement in Government Technical Colleges of Gombe State, Nigeria.
2. Determine the effect of Lecture teaching method on Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students' Achievement in Government Technical Colleges of Gombe State, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were used to guide the study:

1. What is the effect of flipped classroom Instructional Strategy on Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students' Achievement in Government Technical Colleges of Gombe State, Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of Lecture teaching method on Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students' Achievement in Government Technical Colleges of Gombe State, Nigeria?

HYPOTHESES

One hypothesis was formulated by the researcher to support the study:

HO1: There is no significant difference between the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance works trade students taught using the traditional lecture method and those taught using the flipped classroom instructional strategy in GTCs of Gombe State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework

Connectivism is a learning theory developed by George Siemens and Stephen Downes in 2005, which states that knowledge is distributed across networks and involves the ability to recognize and navigate those networks. Connectivism posits out that knowledge is not only acquired through traditional means such as textbooks or lectures but also through online communities, social media, and other technological platforms. According to the theory, learning is an ongoing process of exploration and discovery, and it occurs both within and outside formal educational institutions. Connectivism also suggests that learners must be able to critically evaluate the information they encounter in order to discern what is reliable and relevant. The ability to make connections between different sources of information and knowledge is also critical, as it enables learners to construct new knowledge and adapt to new situations.

As it were, Connectivism provides a valuable perspective on learning in the digital age, highlighting the importance of social networks and technological tools in the learning process. By embracing the principles of Connectivism, learners can acquire the skills and knowledge they need to navigate a rapidly changing world and continue to learn throughout their lives. The relationship of the theory to this study is that they both emphasis on the digital age, highlighting the importance of social networks and technological tools in the teaching and learning process. It stresses that knowledge is distributed across networks of people and resources. Learners must be able to identify and access these networks, and collaborate with others to create new knowledge and understanding, which simply termed as learner's centered method.

Review of Related Empirical Study

Idisape and Akpanaka (2024) conducted a study titled Effect of Flipped Classroom Instructional Model on Students' Achievement in Biology Among Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State. The aim of this study is to assessed the effects of the flipped classroom model on students' biology achievement in secondary schools in Bayelsa State. It has two research questions and two hypotheses. The "quasi-experimental non-equivalent, non-randomised, pre-test, posttest control design was adopted. The study population comprised 2,829 senior secondary two (SS 2) students from the Bayelsa West Senatorial District, as reported by the Bayelsa State Post-Primary Schools Board in 2020. A total of 159 students were selected from four mixed-gender schools in the district using a four-stage sampling process." One hundred and fifty-nine SSS 2 students from four purposively selected public schools in Bayelsa West Senatorial District were assigned to the experimental group (n = 83) and control group (n = 76). The study lasted for six weeks. This study used three instruments: two instructional guides and the "Biology Achievement Test (BAT)." The BAT had a reliability of 0.75 using Kuder Richardson Formula 21 (KR – 21). Data was analysed using mean and standard deviation for the two research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for the two null hypotheses. The findings revealed that the students taught the biology concept using the flipped instructional model outperformed their counterparts taught the same concept using the modified lecture method, and there was no significant gender difference in achievement. It was recommended that the flipped classroom strategy be adopted for teaching biology.

The previous study adopted Quasi-experimental design and also the present study adopted Quasi-experimental design. The studies differ in areas where the present study was conducted in Gombe State while the previous study was conducted in Bayelsa State. The previous study was conducted on Students Achievement in Biology while the present study was carryout on Students Achievement in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade (EIMWT).

METHODOLOGY

This chapter of the study describes, the procedure that was used under the following sub-headings; research design, area of the study, sample and sampling techniques, instrument for data collection, validation of instrument, reliability of the instrument, method of data collection and method of data analysis.

Research Design

The research design adopted for this study was Quasi-experimental design; specifically, the pre-test, post-test non-randomized control group research design was used. This type of design aimed at determining whether there is cause and effect relationship between the variables under study. In this study, students were grouped into experimental and control groups. The experimental group was treated using Flipped Classroom Instructional strategy while the control group was treated using the traditional lecture method. The research design is shown below.

- O₁ = Represent the Pretest Scores of Experimental group one.
- O₃ = Represent the Pretest Scores of Control Group.
- O₂ = Represent the Posttest Scores of Experimental group one.
- O₄ = Represent the Posttest Scores of Control Group.
- X₁ = Treatment given to Experimental group one (flipped classroom instructional strategy).

Area of the Study

The study was conducted in Gombe State of Nigeria. Gombe State is located in Northeastern Nigeria and covers an area of 18,767 square kilometers. It lies at latitudes 10° 15 north' and longitudes 11° 10' East. It is characterized by diverse landscapes, including the Bima hill, and blessed with three multipurpose dams, namely: Cham, Balanga and Dadin Kowa. Bordered with Borno, Yobe, Bauchi, Adamawa and Taraba states, the state is known for its rich cultural heritage. It has a population of 2,365,040 according to census 2006, and 2016 forecast of 3,256962 as reported by Zaccheus, (2024). The study is going to cover the three Educational Zones of Gombe State, which are Gombe north Educational Zone, Gombe Central Educational Zone and Gombe South Educational Zone.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised one hundred and four (104), NTC II Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade (EIMW) students, where ninety-two (92) are male and twelve (12) are female students in the eight (8) government technical colleges in Gombe State.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Multistage sampling technique was used in this study. Firstly, stratified sampling technique was used to select the sample in each educational zone in the state. Secondly, simple random sampling technique was used to assign experimental and control group.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade Achievement Test (EIMWTPT). It was made of up 40 multiple choice names lettered A-D that was adapted from the National Business and

Technical Examination Board (NABTEB) past question papers in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMWT). The students answered the questions by circling the correct option in each question. Each correct answer was marked 1, The topics taught were: Cable Jointing, Electrical Tools and Equipment, Safety in electrical installation and maintenance work, and Domestic Installation.

Validation of Instrument

The draft instrument was face validated by two experts, from the Department of Electrical Technology Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola. The experts appraise the coverage, content, language and adequacy of the draft instrument. The observations, comments and suggestions were used to improve the quality of the instrument before embarking on data collection.

Reliability of the Instrument

In order to ensure the internal consistency of the research instrument, the researcher conducted a trial test of the instrument. The test instrument was administered twice within an interval of two weeks to non-participating students of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade in Government Technical College Bichi, Kano State who has similar characteristics with the participants and are out of the study area. The reliability of 0.731 obtained was determined using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (often abbreviated as PPMC)

Control of Extraneous Variables

In order to test the effect of independent variables, which are the teaching methods (Flipped Classroom and Jigsaw Instructional Strategies), the choice of most appropriate design for the experiment is the basic step. If the factors are not meticulously controlled, they may produce adverse effects, which could confuse the effects of the independent variables. The following are such extraneous variables and their control.

1. Teacher variable: this refers to the teachers' differences in terms of qualification and teaching experiences. In this study in order to control this variable, the researcher selected three research assistants one from each of the technical colleges sampled for experimental group and the control group. The research assistants chosen are of the same qualification and teaching experience.
2. Hawthorne/experimental bias: to avoid this bias, the researcher used simple random sampling to choose one intact class in each technical college. The researcher assigned the school randomly to either experimental or control group.
3. Initial Group Differences: to control initial group differences in the intact groups, statistical control was employed. Pretest was administered to both the experimental and control groups, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used in the data analysis using the pretest scores as covariate.
4. Effect of pretest on posttest/history: history is an unanticipated event occurring while the experiment is in progress; this may affect the dependent variable. To control the influence of history, the interval between pretest and posttest was four weeks.
5. Selection maturation: this refers to selection of subjects from two different groups that have different backgrounds. To reduce the effect of this variable the researcher used only NTC II intact groups of approximately with same age. Pretest was administered to both of the experimental and the control groups to determine students' entry behavior.
6. Testing: this refers to the ability of pretest to provide clue about the posttest. In about to reduce the effect of the extraneous variable, the pretest instrument was reshuffled and printed in different format before it was administered as posttest to avoid remembering of the pretest instrument.

Method of Data Collection

The data was collected by the researcher and three research assistants through the following procedures: The pre-test was administered to both experimental and control groups and pre-test scores obtained. At the end of the intervention, post-test was administered on both experimental group and control groups again with the reshuffle pre-test instrument. This was done with the help of the research assistants from each school under the supervision of the researcher.

Method of Data Analysis

The collected data was analyzed using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while ANCOVA was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

When the Analysis of covariance ANCOVA value or *p*-value was found to be less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis will be rejected, indicating that there is significant difference. On the other hand, when the ANCOVA *p*-value was found to be greater than 0.05 level of alpha, the null hypothesis was upheld, indicating there was no significant difference.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What is the effect of flipped classroom Instructional Strategy on Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade Students’ Achievement in Government Technical Colleges of Gombe State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on effect of flipped classroom Instructional Strategy on Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students’ Achievement

Teaching Method	Test	n	Mean (\bar{x})	S. D. (σ)	Mean Difference
Flipped Classroom	Pre-Test	20	13.80	3.87	10.90
	Post-Test		24.70	4.98	

10.90

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of students’ Achievement scores before and after exposure to the flipped classroom instructional strategy. The result indicates that students had a pre-test mean score of 13.80 (SD = 3.87) before the intervention. After being taught using the flipped classroom strategy, their post-test mean score increased to 24.70 (SD = 4.98). This represents a mean difference of 10.90, suggesting that the flipped classroom instructional strategy substantially improved students’ Achievement in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work.

Research Question Two: What is the effect of Lecture teaching method on Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students’ Achievement in Government Technical Colleges of Gombe State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on effect of Lecture teaching method on Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Students’ Achievement

Teaching Method	Test	n	Mean (\bar{x})	S. D. (σ)	Mean Difference
Lecture	Pre-Test	13	11.53	3.07	8.39
	Post-Test		19.92	4.85	

8.39

Table 2 displays the mean and standard deviation of students’ Achievement scores before and after being taught with the lecture method. The results show that students had a pre-test mean score of 11.53 (SD = 3.07). After the lecture-based instruction, their post-test mean score rose to 19.92 (SD = 4.85). This produced a mean difference of 8.39, indicating that the

lecture teaching method led to an improvement in students' Achievement in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work, although the gain was lower compared to the flipped classroom instructional strategy.

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the academic achievement of electrical installation and maintenance works trade students taught using the traditional lecture method and those taught using the flipped classroom instructional strategy in GTCs of Gombe State, Nigeria.

Table 3: One-way ANCOVA analysis of the post-test mean scores of students taught using the traditional lecture method and those taught using the flipped classroom instructional strategy

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: PostTestScores13

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	830.905 ^a	2	415.452	119.837	.000	.889
Intercept	86.063	1	86.063	24.825	.000	.453
PreTestScores13	651.119	1	651.119	187.815	.000	.862
TeachingMethod13	25.447	1	25.447	7.340	.011	.197
Error	104.005	30	3.467			
Total	18117.000	33				
Corrected Total	934.909	32				

a. R Squared = .889 (Adjusted R Squared = .881)

Table 3 presents the results of the one-way ANCOVA conducted to determine whether a significant difference existed between students' post-test Achievement after controlling for pre-test scores. The analysis revealed a statistically significant effect of teaching method on students' post-test scores, $F(1, 30) = 7.34, p = .011$, partial $\eta^2 = .197$. This indicates that approximately 19.7% of the variance in students' post-test Achievement was explained by the teaching method. Since the significance value ($p < .05$) is less than the alpha level, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, it was concluded that there was a significant difference in the academic Achievement of students taught using the flipped classroom instructional strategy compared to those taught with the traditional lecture method, in favor of the flipped classroom group.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS/RESULTS

The findings of research question one revealed that students taught with the flipped classroom strategy recorded substantial improvement in their Achievement, with a mean gain of 10.90, suggesting that this instructional model is highly effective in enhancing learning in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work. This result is consistent with previous studies which reported that flipped classrooms significantly improve academic Achievement by encouraging active participation and deeper learning (Idisape & Akpanaka, 2024; Isa & Bukar, 2023). Kalat, Yisa, and Sanni (2023) similarly found that flipped learning strategies improved students' achievement and interest in electrical/electronic subjects, showing its relevance for technical education. Oluwashina et al. (2023) further confirmed improved Achievement in practical physics through flipped classrooms, particularly in activity-based and skill-oriented disciplines. Hadi et al. (2022) explained that flipped learning

enhances self-directed learning, problem-solving, and collaboration, which account for its effectiveness. The improvement observed in this study may be attributed to the pre-class exposure of learners to materials, enabling classroom time to be devoted to practical applications and peer interactions that foster deeper conceptual understanding. Hence, the flipped classroom approach provides a robust alternative to traditional instruction, especially in technical and vocational education where active engagement is vital.

The findings of research question two revealed that students taught with the traditional lecture method showed Achievement improvement from a pre-test mean of 11.53 to a post-test mean of 19.92, with a mean gain of 8.39. While this demonstrates that lecture can improve learning, its impact was notably lower than that of flipped classroom strategy. This finding aligns with research showing that teacher-centered approaches often result in surface learning and limited student engagement compared to active methods (Idisape & Akpanaka, 2024; Isa & Bukar, 2023). Ukeh and Anih (2023) emphasized that innovative methods such as flipped classroom are superior to traditional lectures in promoting deeper understanding. Similarly, Kalat, Yisa, and Sanni (2023) observed that reliance on lecture methods in technical education restricts practical application and learner autonomy, leading to lower Achievement outcomes. Hadi et al. (2022) also noted that lecture-based instruction lacks the flexibility and interactivity needed for skill-oriented disciplines. The current result shows that while lecture methods can lead to modest gains, they remain less effective for technical subjects requiring higher-order thinking and practical engagement. This underscores the need to complement lecture approaches with active learning strategies like flipped classroom for improved Achievement.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of this study was to ascertain the effects of flipped classroom, on students' academic Achievement in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works in government technical colleges in Gombe State, Nigeria. From the findings, it can be inferred that flipped classroom significantly enhanced students' achievement compared to the conventional lecture method. Furthermore, the study established that while flipped classroom was effective in improving Achievement, it proved superior to lecture by promoting deeper understanding, collaboration, and application of knowledge. These outcomes provide strong evidence that learner-centered strategies such as flipped classroom is not only engaging instructional tools but also pedagogically sound approaches for advancing achievement in technical and vocational education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made:

1. Since the flipped classroom strategy significantly improved students' Achievement, technical college teachers should adopt this approach by providing pre-class learning materials (videos, notes, simulations) and using classroom time for problem-solving and hands-on practice.
2. As lecture proved less effective compared to innovative methods, technical colleges should minimize over-reliance on the traditional lecture approach and combine it with learner-centered strategies to boost students' engagement and achievement.

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